

New extraction-spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) with potassium isobutyl xanthate

B. Sreenivasa Rao^{a*}, K. Ramakrishna^a and P. Venkateswarlu^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, College of Engineering, GITAM, Visakhapatnam-530 045, India

E-mail : battula-sr@yahoo.com Fax : 91-891-2790399

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. V. University, College of Engineering, Tirupathi-517 502, India

Manuscript received 6 August 2002, revised 25 February 2003, accepted 4 March 2003

A simple and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of iron(III) based on the reaction of iron(III) with potassium isobutyl xanthate (KIBX). The absorbance of the complex is measured spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 378 nm at pH 5.0. The molar absorptivity of the complex is $2.58 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 2.5–35.0 mg of iron(III). The method is sensitive and selective and has been applied to the determination of iron(III) in the selected food and pharmaceutical samples.

Various spectrophotometric, and atomic absorption spectrometric methods have been developed to estimate iron¹. A literature survey indicates that very few xanthates² have been explored for the extractive-spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. The present communication reports the results of our investigation on the use of potassium isobutyl xanthate (KIBX) for the extractive-spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) *per se* and in selected food and pharmaceutical formulations.

Results and discussion

Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) is used as the solvent for extraction of the metal complex in which it is freely soluble, and complete extraction of the complex needs just 2 min. The complex attains maximum intensity with an eight-fold excess of the reagent (1.0 ml of 0.5% of the reagent) and the pH being adjusted to 5.0.

Beer-Lambert's law is found to be applicable in the concentration range 2.5–35.0 ppm. From the slope of the Ringbom plot, the relative error in the concentration is calculated to be 0.0138. The optimum concentration range for accurate determination of iron(III) by the proposed method is found to be 5.0–30.0 ppm. Sandel's sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complex have been calculated to be $2.1647 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $2.58 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The standard deviation and the coefficient of the variance are 0.8689×10^{-3} and 0.372%, respectively.

The composition of iron(III) complex is determined to be 1 : 3 (M : L) according to mole-ratio, Asmu's and Job's methods. The instability constant of the complex is found to be 2.4377×10^{-10} by Edmonds and Birnbaum's method.

The effect of diverse ions on the extractive-spectrophotometric determination of Fe^{III} reveals that cations like U^{VI} and Sr^{II} do not have any effect on the extraction of Fe(KIBX)₃ complex up to 4500 μg , while Ce^{II} does not interfere even when present up to 2000 μg , Co^{II}, Ni^{II} can be tolerated up to 500 μg . Pb^{II}, Cr^{VI} and Cu^{II} interfere seriously. Anions like acetate, tartrate and chloride do not interfere when present up to 5000 μg . Bicarbonate and sulfate can be tolerated up to 3000 μg .

It is evident that KIBX is a sensitive reagent for the extraction-spectrophotometric determination of iron(III). Hence the use of KIBX as an extractant in the separation of Fe^{III} from several other associated metal ions is commendable.

The results indicate that the proposed method can be regarded as an alternative to the determination of iron(III) by a more sensitive method. By applying this procedure to the analysis of real samples, a recovery of 96.5–99.2% was achieved.

Applications :

Determination of iron(III) content in food samples was carried out using the present method. 10.0 g of dried food determinant was weighed and brought into the solution by dry ash method³. The iron content is found to be 1.011 mg, 0.993 mg and 0.732 mg/10 g samples of *Piper betle*, soyabean and peas, respectively. This is in good agreement with the standard thiocyanate method. The percentage recovery in these samples are 97.0, 96.9 and 96.5, respectively.

The method was also applied for the determination of iron(III) in pharmaceutical samples like Impheron injection,

Fecontin F tablets and Ferrochelate drops. For all these pharmaceutical samples, the metal content was brought into the solution by using the standard procedure³. The amount of iron(III) is found to be 49.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1.95 mg/ml and 1.31 mg/ml, respectively, as against 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2 mg/ml and 1.33 mg/ml in Infeon injection, Fecontin F tablets and Ferrochelate drops, respectively. The recovery in all the three samples are 99.2, 97.5 and 98.5% respectively.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. A stock solution ($\sim 0.1\text{ M}$) of iron(III) was prepared and standardized⁴. The stock solution was suitably diluted as and when required to give the working solution (0.01 mol dm^{-3}). Buffer solution was prepared by using 0.2 mol dm^{-3} acetic acid and 0.2 mol dm^{-3} sodium acetate in suitable ratios. KIBX was prepared by literature method⁵ and its 0.5% solution was prepared in water. The solvent MIBK was used as such.

A Shimadzu PR-I spectrophotometer and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

General procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing 25–550 μg of iron(III), 0.2 mol dm^{-3} acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.0) solution (2 ml) and 0.5% KIBX solution (3.0 ml) were added, and the total volume was made up to 10 ml by deionized distilled water. The

light brown coloured Fe^{III} -KIBX complex formed was extracted into MIBK (10 ml) and its absorbance was measured at 378 nm against the reagent blank.

References

1. M. Kass and A. Ivaska., *Talanta*, 2002, **58**, 1131; D. Kara and M. Alkan., *Talanta*, 2001, **55**, 415; H. Abdollahi, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **442**, 327; A. M. G. Rodriguez, A. G. Torres, J. M. C. Pavon and C. B. Ojeda, *Talanta*, 1998, **47**, 463; A. K. Malik and A. L. J. Rao, *Talanta*, 1997, **44**, 173; M. I. Toral, P. Richter and C. Rodriguez, *Talanta*, 1997, **45**, 147; M. A. Zayed, B. N. Barsoum and A. E. Hassan, *Microchem. J.*, 1996, **54**, 72; M. Y. Khuhawar and J. P. Das, *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.*, 1997, **19**, 278.
2. K. V. S. Murthy, T. Balaji, P. R. Devi and G. R. K. Naidu, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1993, **9**, 13; A. K. Malik, K. N. Kaul, B. S. Lark, W. Faubel and A. L. J. Rao, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 99; A. K. Malik and A. L. J. Rao, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2000, **55**, 746; A. K. Malik, *Ann. Chim.*, 2000, **90**, 581; P. R. Reddy and P. C. Sekhar, *J. Radionucl. Chem.*, 1995, 181; Y. Nagosa and T. Mizuyuki, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1995, **311**, 225.
3. A. Stewarte, H. M. Grimshaw, J. Parkinson and Q. Christopher. "Chemical Analysis of Ecological Materials", Blackwell, Oxford, London, 1974.
4. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th. ed., Longman, London, 1961.
5. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longman, London, 1968.